

Report

Analysis of potential markets for using
technologies in the superconducting
magnet value chain

*Scrap Metal Recycling and
Fruit Sorting and Grading*

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Executive Summary

Aim & Method:

This investigation evaluates the industrial impact potentials for two technologies needed in the manufacturing process of superconducting magnets for particle colliders. On the one hand, the goal is to provide a qualitative and quantitative evaluation of the market potential of a furnace technology used to make Rutherford cables superconductive and to assess its relevance in the scrap metal recycling industry. On the other hand, it determines the willingness to pay and provides a comparison with current technologies on the market for fruit sorting and grading via NMR spectroscopy. Pursuing a qualitative approach, over 50 interviews with industry experts were conducted. Based on those insights, different strategic tools and frameworks were applied in order to reach the defined objectives.

Results for Scrap Metal Recycling:

Present high-potential market: Furnace technology currently provide the most value within the aluminum recycling industry. Especially the use of electricity as its fuel instead of gas sets it apart from current solutions on the market.

Need for technology adaption: To enter new markets, the furnace's max. temperature needs to be enhanced since the its use benefits unfold their biggest potential within the precious metals recycling industry where temperatures above 961°C are required.

Future high-potential market: Introducing the furnace technology to the precious metals recycling market is recommended since the furnace's use benefits are the most effective and relevant within this particular industry.

Results for Fruit Sorting, grading and related application areas:

Present high-potential market: Overall, the targeted buyer groups in the industry show a high interest in NMR spectroscopy. However, the estimated value is low since there is only limited need for such a high degree of technology preciseness. Secondly, the price of the NMR-based technology exceeds the average budget available for sorting or grading machines in the industry.

Need for technology adaption: If the technology is to enter the market, it is essential to lower costs, extend the range of measurable parameters and increase the sampling speed in order to create a competitive advantage over already existing technologies.

Future high-potential market: A market entrance is recommended since the technology ensures a non-invasive method to sort and grade fruits in terms of different parameters in addition to the degree of ripeness. A novel potential application field for NMR spectroscopy could be in-ovo sexing for chicken eggs which could enable companies to prevent chick culling. Quality assurance in niche markets such as vanilla, a high-market value agricultural product should be further analysed, since the customers' willingness to pay may outweigh the high investment costs of superconducting devices.

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List of Abbreviations

CERN	Conseil Européen pour la Recherche Nucléaire
EU27	EU member states except for the UK
FCC	Future Circular Collider
LHC	Large Hadron Collider
NMR	Nuclear Magnetic Resonance
OECD	Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development
SMR	Scrap metal recycling
UPS	Uninterruptible Power Supply

1 Introduction

The European Organisation for Nuclear Research, CERN, derived from Conseil européen pour la recherche nucléaire, is the biggest European research organization that operates the largest particle physics laboratory in the world. It was established in 1954 by its 12 founding states and is based in Geneva, Switzerland. Currently, it has 23 member states with others being in the pre-stage to membership. CERN is governed by a Council of Member State representatives. The Council sets the organization's policy and is assisted by the Scientific Policy Committee and the Finance Committee. The current Director-General is Dr. Fabiola Gianotti (CERN, n.d).

The main fields of activity at CERN involve the Large Hadron Collider (LHC), the world's largest and most powerful particle accelerator with a 27-kilometer ring of superconducting magnets buried 100 meters underground. The LHC accelerates protons and ions at a velocity approaching the speed of light which then collide with each other. The captured data is then analyzed. Scientists hope that the Large Hadron Collider will help answer many of the fundamental open questions in physics. While the main focus of research at CERN has moved in recent years towards the LHC, experiments at other accelerators and facilities remain an essential part of the laboratory's activities. This diverse research program ensures that CERN covers a wide range of topics in physics (CERN, n.d). A recent example of a research project is the Future Circular Colliders (FCC) Study, which is developing designs for a higher performance particle collider (CERN, n.d)

1.1 Case Definition

In order to investigate the fundamental building blocks of our universe, CERN still heavily relies on custom-made technologies which are only available at a very high cost. Especially the manufacturing of novel high-field superconductive magnets is considered a significant cost driver for CERN. In past projects, key processes of the manufacturing value-chain of the superconductive magnet technology have been assessed according to their industrial impact potential. After that, new innovative alternative application fields outside the particle-accelerator domain for the technologies used in the most promising process steps were identified. One of the most promising application fields turned out to be scrap metal recycling via heat-based separation as well as fruit sorting & grading via NMR spectroscopy. This current project acts as a follow-up project to analyze the two high-potential application fields in detail.

1.2 Project Background

Previous projects of the Entrepreneurship and Innovation Institute at the Vienna University of Economics (Austria) identified the most important industrial application fields outside the particle-accelerator domain for various technologies needed for building novel, high-field superconductive magnets. A total of 67 potential application areas were identified in the past two projects.

1.2.1 Superconductor Manufacturing Process in a New Context (2018)

The past project with the goal to identify alternative industrial application fields for technologies and processes applied in the manufacturing of superconducting magnets discovered a total of 38 new application fields. More precisely, the production steps to be analyzed were “superconducting Rutherford cables” (15), “thermal treatment” (10) and “vacuum impregnation with novel epoxy” (13). The study then suggested some high potential application fields. Within these categories, one of the most promising application turned out to be scrap metal recycling mainly due to its high relevance in the future, and the uniqueness of the features of CERN’s furnace compared to current solutions on the market. For the process, CERN’s furnace technology, which is typically used to make Rutherford cables superconductive, is used to melt down different scrap metals into their primary components via heat-based separation.

1.2.2 Identifying New Fields of Application for Superconductors (2017)

This project’s task was to find new application fields for superconducting magnets. In total 29 new application fields were discovered, from which the three most promising findings turned out to be: Uninterruptible Power Supply (UPS), sorting machines for the fruit industry and large loudspeaker systems. In a second step, the high potential areas were analyzed in further detail including a market analysis, a business development strategy as well as certain technology adoptions needed for commercialization. In particular the fruit sorting industry was identified as a promising field of application for superconductors. The technology enables companies to determine the grade of ripeness, amount of seeds and density of fruits in a non-destructive way and consequently reduces the amount of disposal and waste while increasing the quality of delivered fruits.

1.3 Project Goal

The goal of this study is to provide a qualitative and quantitative evaluation of the market potential of CERN’s furnace technology and its relevance in the scrap metal recycling industry on the one hand. On the other hand, it aims to determine the perceived value of the technology and provides a comparison with current solutions on the market for the fruit sorting and grading process. Currently, both of these processes are supported by other technologies and, therefore, the goal is to assess and promote the potential of these two alternatives in the current market. Providing information about the external and

internal environment as well as delivering a sound strategy regarding CERN's future course of action for scrap metal recycling via heat-based separation is the first pillar of this report. The second pillar of this report is a rigorous analysis concerning the customers perceived attractiveness and value estimation for the fruit sorting and grading technology.

2 Methodology

This chapter provides an overview of the project approach, method, applied tools and overall structure of the project in respect to the two different tasks. The two projects have different objectives and, therefore, various different and complementary tools and analyses are used. The approach is similar, except for the analyses and the tools applied. It is an iterative interaction of expert interviews and analyses. First, the projects' starting point and possible directions are set through a deep dive via secondary research into the subject matter. From there, the gathered knowledge through expert interviews is the input for the strategic analyses. Based on the findings, further interviews are conducted whose generated insights are again included in the analyses. The result is an iterative process that enables agile working and the generation of relevant recommendations. Additionally, pyramiding is used to search for further experts in the respective industries. This particular method aims at finding the most knowledgeable experts through referral to fellow professionals in their field, which dramatically enhances the time and effort needed to find essential industry experts (Franke, 2018). In the following chapters, the project-specific tasks are explained in further detail.

2.1 Scrap Metal Recycling

The scrap metal recycling industry is analyzed by combining both, tools used for the assessment of external factors as well as internal factors of the industry. For reasons discussed in further detail in section 3.2, the external and internal analysis will focus mainly on the aluminum industry, and additionally assess the potential of the furnace for the market with the highest potential in the future.

The external analysis of the aluminum industry consists of a general market overview, including the volume, potential, and growth of the market as well as customer trends and needs. Moreover, the market overview sets a particular focus on ecological factors since they entail the most relevant macro-environmental aspects for the future of scrap metal recycling. Secondly, the value chain of the aluminum industry is depicted in order to enable a holistic visualization of the relevant actors in the aluminum industry. Lastly, a competitive analysis provides insights into the overall attractiveness of the technology's environment. Therefore, Porter's Five Forces Framework is deployed, which is a tool developed by Michael Porter to examine the most relevant forces influencing the environment of a particular industry or technology. The primary goal is to find a position in the industry where the technology can best defend itself against the five forces or can affect them in its favor (Müller-Stewens, 2011).

An internal analysis is performed by assessing the furnaces use benefits according to the opinions of various industry experts as well as recycling companies. The assessment culminates in a technology attractiveness pentagon. The pentagon is a visualization of the perceived attractiveness of the furnace's use benefits in a particular industry. The pentagon is made up of four layers and scaled from 1 to 4, where 1 suggests a low interest and 4 suggests a very high interest in the use benefits of the furnace. Furthermore, it entails a Business Model Canvas, which outlines the recommended business structure. The Business Model Canvas is a tool developed by Henry Chesbrough to visualize and analyze business structures by depicting them in nine building blocks. The building blocks represent the most vital aspects companies have to take into account in order to succeed. Therefore, it helps to optimize the business model and analyze it in a more detailed way (Osterwalder & Pigneur, 2010).

In the last phase, key insights are pulled together and specific recommendations are provided. For the recommendation, a three-horizon perspective offers information regarding the urgency of the recommended actions.

2.2 Fruit Sorting and Grading

Firstly, the fruit sorting and grading industry is analyzed by comparing CERN's technology to its competitors. A matrix addressing the invasiveness, preciseness and practicability is used to give an overview of other commonly used technologies and methods in the fruit sorting industry.

Secondly, the supply chain in the industry is analyzed. Three different potential buyer groups are analyzed in detail, addressing advantages, disadvantages and the estimated potential. From the same three buyer groups, a value estimation for the NMR-based fruit sorting technology is generated. This information is depicted in a graph, which additionally compares the actual price of the NMR spectroscopy technology to these estimations.

The recommendations for fruit sorting and grading entail a market entry strategy and an assessment of technology's perceived attractiveness. A technology attractiveness hexagon is used, showing six different parameters of the technology, which would need to be enhanced in order to enter the market successfully and be competitive. This hexagon is based on four different performance levels, with 1 being unattractive and 4 being highly attractive according to expert opinions.

2.3 Milestone Plan

The graphic below shows the project progress and marks critical points regarding the course of the project. The milestone plan's purpose is to give an overview and outline of the structure of the project.

Figure 1: Project schedule with milestones

3 Analysis Scrap Metal Recycling

Scrap metal recycling was identified as one of the most promising application fields for CERN’s furnace technology used in the manufacturing process of high-field superconductive magnets. The following analysis will provide a detailed analysis of the furnace’s potential in that field. The general idea is to separate different types of metals using their specific melting points. Therefore, the furnace heats up to a specific temperature and remains at that temperature until the targeted metal is wholly separated from the other materials.

Figure 2: Scrap metal collection center (Max Pixel, 2016)

Figure 3: Process step of Aluminum recycling (UC Rusal Photo Gallery, 2014)

3.1 Technology Use Benefits & Learnings

The following section is an assessment of the use benefits of the furnace for the scrap metal recycling industry. The improvements of the furnace’s features are outlined and explained below and are the outcome of the cooperation between CERN and the furnace manufacturer Gero Carbolite, which resulted in an innovation outcome. Furthermore, Gero Carbolite was not only able to manufacture

CERN's special furnace, but gained valuable knowledge and now possesses a model, a computer simulation as well as in-house knowledge for the construction and manufacturing of specialized furnaces (Gutleber, 2019). The company has not only gained in reputation but also experienced a learning effect, clearly making it more competitive in the market.

Figure 4 CERN's Furnace Technology for Heat Treatment (Lackner, 2016)

Homogenous Heating

Within the special furnace every single particle can be thoroughly heated over a time period of more than 200 hours. The homogeneity is completely dissociated from the size of the furnace, leading to flexible scaling of the furnace without a loss in temperature control and stability (Ohnweiler, 2019).

Heating Speed

During heat treatment, the temperature in the furnace can be altered at a rate of 50 K per hour. The furnace heats up in stable time intervals with short breaks in between each interval. For heating the entire system (loading included) to the max. temperature of 900 °C the furnace needs a total performance of around 400 kW (Ohnweiler, 2019).

Temperature Preciseness

A fan, which enables circulation of the protective gas argon during heat treatment, in combination with 14 heating zones inside the furnace gives it the ability to react to temperature deviations quickly and enables to reach the perfect temperature within a +/- 3 °C range (Ohnweiler, 2019). This makes the heating process substantially more precise since normal industry furnaces, like for instance, in the steel industry, can only assure a maximum variance of +/- 10 °C (Berger & Dickert, 2018). The consequence is overheating, which does lead to a deterioration of the materials quality and is not an unusual phenomenon in such industries (Hörtnagl, 2018).

Less Corrosion due to Protective Gas

Within the furnace, argon is used as a protective gas to minimize corrosion. The oxidation of materials would lead to a substantial shrinkage of materials and, therefore, to an inefficient process (Ohnweiler, 2019).

Reduction of Costs and Sustainability

Current industry furnaces are often still heated with unsustainable fuel gas, thereby simultaneously harming the environment. Since CERN's furnace is operating with electricity, green energy can be used. Furthermore, electricity-based heating leads to an improved energy efficiency since the furnace only consumes energy when actually in use and only as much as precisely needed (Gutleber, 2019). Thus, the improved furnace consumes less energy, and uses a sustainable resource for heating, reducing the cost of operation and the negative effect on third parties and the environment.

3.2 External Analysis

This section provides a market overview, insights into the structure of the industry value chain as well as an analysis of the competitive environment recycling furnaces are facing in the aluminum industry. The market analysis will be narrowed down to the European market and will exclude all metal industries apart from the aluminum industry since all other metals industries were identified as currently unsuitable application fields for the furnace technology. The main reasons for the exclusion of the majority of metal industries are the temperature restrictions of the furnace – limited to 900 °C – since most metals need higher temperatures in order to be smelted. Furthermore, the unsuitable composition of input resources of other major industries such as in electronic scrap recycling (e.g. the separation of metal from plastic leaves an unusable slag behind) as well as the frequent referral to the aluminum industry by both companies and various industry experts indicates that currently, the highest potential lies within the aluminum industry (Ek, et al., 2019).

3.2.1 Market Overview

The global aluminum demand is primarily driven by construction, automotive, and aerospace industries, where the metal has replaced steel in many cases. Around 75% of all aluminum ever manufactured, dating back as far as 125 years, is still in use today since it can be recycled after each use phase with a loss of material of almost zero (Nappi, 2013). The European aluminum scrap metal recycling market entails a total of more than 300 recycling plants (International Aluminium Institute, 2009).

Figure 5: Total and relative production forecast for primary and recycled Aluminum worldwide.

Secondary Al production (recycled aluminum that is used for production again) in Europe increased by 21.6% to 2.906 mn tons from 2010 to 2015. In contrast, the primary aluminum production in Europe decreased by approximately 8.5% to 7.897 mn tons from 2010 to 2015 (Bureau of International Recycling, 2016). For reference, the world total went up by 30.8% to 16.614 mn tons over the same period, thus showing a positive trend with aluminum recycling, which is due to the increased demand by the industries stated above. (Bureau of International Recycling, 2016). In the last years, the aluminum recycling markets experienced continual growth. This increase is caused by the rise in urban population, growing concerns about the depletion of natural resources. Due to the stagnation of the primary aluminum production and the increase of aluminum recycling activities, the gap of their relative contributions diminishes (see: Figure 6 Total and Relative Production Forecast for Primary and Recycled Aluminum Worldwide).

Ecological Factors

Generally, it is assumed that the European industry strives towards more sustainable business operations and resource management in the future. The production of secondary aluminum greatly reduces CO₂ emissions compared to primary aluminum production. Therefore, especially ecological aspects will impact the level of commitment towards fostering the aluminum recycling industry.

The cause of sustainability is both fostered by the governments of Europe as well as by customers, who increasingly demand sustainable business processes and resource management. The primary production of aluminum still needs vast amounts of electricity compared to other metal industries.

Currently, the primary aluminum production needs around 160-200 GJ/ton compared to 8-20 GJ/ton in the secondary aluminum production (Bureau of International Recycling, 2018). This huge difference in electricity needed implies not only an economic cost, but also an ecological one (Antrekowitsch, 2019). Furthermore, the increasing awareness of ecological problems in industries among the population will positively affect the future relevance of aluminum recycling.

Figure 6: Annual avoided emission by aluminum recycling.

3.2.2 Industry Value Chain

The following section presents the value chain for aluminum recycling technologies, as well as the connections between the participants in this market.

Figure 7: Industry value chain of aluminum recycling.

The industry value chain of the aluminum recycling technologies is comprised of the suppliers, followed by a limited number of furnace manufacturers which have strong relationships with their respective customers since furnace manufacturers in Europe provide whole recycling systems rather than individual products (Shailesh, 2019). Servicing helps manufacturers retain their customers and also

provides room for companies purely focused on the servicing aspect. The list of customers ranges from multinationals to local companies with a sufficiently large budget for the manufacturer's solutions. Industry experts are another aspect of the value chain that must be considered. They function as an intermediary as they connect key players vertically and horizontally across the steps in the value chain (Hafner, 2019).

3.2.3 Competitive Analysis

The following section of the report focuses on the competitive environment aluminum recycling technologies are facing. Using Porter's Five Forces Framework, different external forces which influence the attractiveness of the technology environment are analyzed.

Figure 8 Porter's Five Forces

Bargaining Power of Suppliers – Medium

A crucial partnership for the technology providers are the suppliers of fireproof claddings. The fireproof claddings inside the furnaces have to be replaced on a regular basis due to erosion (Antrekowitsch, 2019). Since only very few companies offer these services, the furnace manufactures face a small supplier group in this particular category (Wagner, 2019). However, most of the components needed for the manufacturing process have multiple suppliers. This mixed bargaining power suggests a certain degree of dependency on suppliers for technology providers.

Bargaining Power of Buyers – Low

The bargaining power of recycling companies strongly depends on their special technological requirements. Most of the big companies do not buy individual furnaces, but rather a whole recycling system with harmonized processes in order to assure a smooth functionality of the whole process. These systems can cost as much as 15 - 20 million euro and are, therefore, investments that not only need a

trustful partner but also require proof of functionality, which especially established suppliers can provide (Shailesh, 2019). This implies a good bargaining position for technology providers' incremental innovations within new holistic recycling systems since there is a substantial cost of switching to another provider. However, for new technologies entering the market, it can be hard to convince buyers of their new products.

Threats of New Entrants – Low

Due to the mature market for scrap metal recycling technologies, the threat of new entrants in the furnace manufacturing business is low, since the industry is characterized by economies of scale, brand loyalty, high capital requirements, and high switching costs (Antrekowitsch, 2019). This implies high entry barriers for new technologies trying to enter the market.

Threats of Substitutes – Low

The threat of substitute technologies other than furnace technologies is estimated low since smelting is assumed to be highly effective in fulfilling the needed recycling efficiency of the industry. Furthermore, the threat of substitutes for smelting technologies is estimated low as well, since European furnace manufactures specialized in providing whole recycling systems rather than just individual products to increase the recycling companies switching costs and consequently counteract the threat of low-cost products from Asia (Shailesh, 2019). Therefore, not only the capital employed is substantial, but also knowledge about the particular requirements of the companies lies with the furnace manufacturer. This greatly enhances the perceived product differentiation of the incumbent technologies and reduces threat of substitution.

Technology Rivalry – Medium

The general rivalry among competing furnace technologies is balanced. On the one hand, growing demand for recycling activities implies a high market potential for the technologies (Bureau of International Recycling, 2016). Furthermore, brand loyalty and high switching costs foster long-term relationships between the manufacturer and the recycling company, thus, decreasing rivalry among the technologies (Shailesh, 2019). However, high capital investments needed for those technologies pose a substantial exit barrier for firms in the industry. This means that even inefficient technologies might not exit the industry due to the risk of losing substantial investments and, thus, increasing the rivalry on the market. Moreover, the current supply of recyclable metals is limited due to the long industry lifetime of aluminum (e.g., Cars tie-up aluminum for as much as 10-15 years). Therefore, capacity expansions of recycling companies are only incremental, which implies a sluggish but consistent increase in demand for industrial recycling furnaces (Antrekowitsch, 2019).

3.3 Internal Analysis

The internal analysis examines the use benefits of the furnace and points out the necessary technology adaptations needed to reach a bigger market potential. Moreover, it provides a canvas, which allows to optimize the business model and analyze it in a more detailed way.

3.3.1 Assessment of the Furnace's Use Benefits in the Aluminum Industry

The assessment of the furnace's use benefits is the appraisal of the responses of recycling companies as well as various industry experts within the aluminum recycling industry and depicts the general interest and attractiveness of the features of the furnace in a particular industry. Figure 9 shows the assessment of the five use benefits on a scale from 1 to 4.

The homogenous heating of the furnace has only a modest impact on the attractiveness of the product since smelting does not require a high level of temperature homogeneity (Ek, et al., 2019). Furthermore, the precise temperature regulation is only of marginal interest to the aluminum industry since current technologies already fulfill the necessary requirements (Scheele, Kopils, & Canaval, 2019). Although the protective gas argon

Figure 9: Use benefit assessment for aluminum recycling.

undeniably leads to less corrosion during the smelting of metals, its high price poses a significant disadvantage for the aluminum recycling industry. Since the furnaces have to be opened regularly during the recycling process, most of the argon would escape from the furnace and would need to be refilled every time after opening the furnace (Antrekowitsch, 2019). Therefore, current technologies use slag instead of argon, which provides a much cheaper alternative to the noble gas (Antrekowitsch, Duspiva, Scheele, & Hoffmann, 2019). Moreover, the heating speed of 50K per hour is according to various companies and experts relatively slow in comparison to current technologies in the scrap metal recycling business (Duspiva, Ek, Scheele, Antrekowitsch, & Hoffmann, 2019). Lastly, the use of electricity instead of gas for heating the furnace is something most companies assess as an essential step into a more sustainable future, but only in combination with eco-friendly electricity. However, as long as eco-friendly electricity is not available at a sufficient scale, most companies keep using gas due to its cheaper price on the market (Antrekowitsch & Scheele, 2019).

3.3.2 Technology Adaptions

Since the CERN/Gero co-developed technology has a maximum temperature reach of 900 °C, most metals cannot be melted. However, if the furnaces use benefits could be sustained while simultaneously increasing its heating performance it would be a promising technology for the recycling of precious metals (Löbbus, Bartley, & Antrekowitsch, 2019). Moreover, increasing the heating speed of the furnace is advised since current technologies have a higher heating speed than 50 K per hour (Duspiva, Ek, Scheele, Antrekowitsch, & Hoffmann, 2019). This situation is depicted in Figure 10.

Figure 10 Use Benefit Assessment: Precious Metals

Especially the use of argon as a protective gas is convenient since the loss of substance due to oxidation implies a much higher cost when smelting precious metals compared to high volume metals like aluminum, steel and iron (Löbbus, Bartley, & Antrekowitsch, 2019). In order to enter the precious metals recycling market, the technology would need to reach a temperature of 961°C for silver, 1063°C for gold and 1083°C for copper.

3.3.3 Business Model Canvas

The Business Model Canvas was first introduced by Henry Chesbrough. The template structures the business model into nine segments, which help to identify, align, and visualize interdependences of the relevant activities. The relevant building blocks are: Key Partners, Key Activities, Key Resources, Value Proposition, Customer Relationships, Channels, Customer Segments, Cost Structure, Revenue Streams.

CERN		CERN/Industry Partner		Industry Partner
Key Partners experts in the recycling industry furnace manufacturers	Key Activities technology adaption exploitation of current markets exploration of new application fields	Value Proposition state-of-the-art furnace technology raising awareness for superconductor technology and learning effects from cooperation with CERN	Customer Relationship long term oriented contract-based	Customer Segments furnace manufacturers
	Key Resources alignment of complementary processes market insights R&D regarding furnace technology adaptations		Channels project-based knowledge transfer	
Cost Structure R&D promotion maintenance		Revenue Streams licensing of technology improvements technology updates and maintenance		

Figure 11: Business model canvas for aluminum recycling technology.

Value proposition

The value proposition is a sophisticated furnace technology with several use benefits compared to current furnaces in the market. These use benefits are the product of the cooperation between CERN and Gero Carbolite. Moreover, it provides a sustainable alternative to current solutions within the aluminum recycling industry. The new technology is, therefore, providing improved performance while simultaneously being highly relevant in the future since CSR initiatives are gaining momentum and both customers, as well as employees, demand sustainable business solutions (Antrekowitsch, 2019).

Customer Relations

Since both furnace manufactures as well as recycling companies can be customers of the technology, the pool of potential partners is vast. However, it is still advised to pick long-term customer relationships with a few particular companies in order to guarantee a vivid exchange of knowledge and information and maximize the learning effects on both sides. This way, the customers would not only profit from the already improved furnace but could just like Gero Carbolite, improve the technology even further. This would create an upward spiral from which the whole recycling industry could profit.

Customer Segments

The most important end customer for the technology will be recycling companies with a strong orientation towards sustainability. However, since most furnace technologies are sold as whole recycling systems rather than single products the most important customer for CERN will be other

furnace manufacturers (Shailesh, 2019). Since recycling companies value the outcomes of the cooperation between CERN and Gero Carbolite, they should not change their approach. Thus, instead of providing a direct impact through the cooperation with recycling companies, they generate a positive impact indirectly through improving features and processes of the technologies of furnace manufacturers. In the end, both furnace, as well as recycling companies, benefit from the technological advancements.

Channels

Since the essential factors are an efficient knowledge transfer between CERN and its customers as well as the exploitation of their potential learning from each other, the best channel would be long-term oriented projected-based knowledge transfer.

Revenue Streams

Since CERN receives vast amounts of public investments, these funds not only have to advance the cause of exploring our universe but also have to impact the current industry positively. Therefore, CERN should increase their return on investment by licensing the technological advancements, which it gained through its cooperations, to other furnace manufacturers.

Cost Structure

The costs depend on further research and development efforts. Additional costs drivers are the promotion and communication of the technology improvements and its regular maintenance. The actual cost structure is highly relevant and should be investigated in further depth. However, since an analysis of the cost structure goes beyond the scope of this project it is not part of this report.

Key Partners

Experts in the scrap metal recycling industry are crucial key partners. They provide the required market insights which are needed to successfully enter the market. Moreover, they enlarge CERN's industry-specific knowledge. Other critical key partners are furnace manufacturers. Like Gero Carbolite, they can benefit from improvements and learning curves due to the cooperation with CERN.

Key Activities

Key resources enable the implementation of key activities. The most essential activities would be the adaption of the furnace technology, the exploitation of markets which currently hold the most potential and exploration of new application fields. Technology adaption addresses the internal optimization of the technology. Most urgently needed is the increase of the furnaces heating performance in order to be able to smelt precious metals.

Key Resources

In order to guarantee the best possible outcomes for CERN and its industry partners, some key resources are required on both sides. For the industry partners, the alignment of complementary processes is needed to ensure a smooth implementation of the technology. Market insights on the other hand, help CERN to exploit current markets and explore new application fields. Moreover, further R&D regarding the furnace's technology adaptations is crucial to increase its potential and to attract more customers.

4 Analysis of Fruit Sorting and Grading

This chapter provides three different analyses on the application of NMR spectroscopy in the fruit sorting and grading industry. Firstly, a competitor analysis is carried out in which NMR spectroscopy is compared to other technologies used for fruit sorting and grading. Next, three different targeted buyer groups are analyzed (customer discovery). Advantages, disadvantages and an estimated potential for each customer group are presented in detail. Lastly, a value estimation of the technology is performed. As the fruit market is internationally orientated and producers and distributors benefit from globalization, the analyses of the willingness to pay for CERN's technology as well as the comparison of advantages and disadvantages of substitutes refer to the global market.

4.1 Ripening Process and Technology Description

Technology Description and Application

In the NMR spectroscopy module, a sample is transported through a strong magnetic field generated by a superconductor. The object itself becomes magnetic for a short time and, therefore, has its own magnetic field, its strength depending on its water content. This process happens due to the fact that water molecules align themselves particularly easily in a magnetic field because of their chemical structure. Accordingly, an object with high-water content has a stronger magnetic field after the magnetization process than an object in which hardly any water molecules are present. Subsequently, this magnetic field is measured in the NMR module using a pickup coil. In a final step, the recorded data is compared with a database, from which information about the internal properties of the object can be deduced (Kosse, 2019).

This procedure can be used to control the quality of the fruits and vegetables. Firstly, in the case of climacteric fruits, which have a post ripening process after being harvested, it can determine the degree of ripeness, since the water content in the fruit changes depending on the stage of ripeness. The main advantage of analyzing the water content is the speed of the procedure (Kosse, 2019). Secondly, NMR spectroscopy can also be used for grading since it can detect parasites and other impurities. For example, Stolbur is a common potato disease and a big problem for farmers. "At an early stage, the disease is usually not detectable without destroying the body" (Staudigl, 2019). Parasites like click beetles or wireworms can be identified without destroying the outer layer of the fruits and vegetables. "The composition of the inner values changes because cavities cause a difference in the air-content of the fruit" (Gössinger, 2019). Lastly, a quality loss can occur during the storage of the fruits and vegetables (Wurm, 2019).

4.2 Competitor Analysis

NMR spectroscopy is not yet introduced in the fruit sorting and grading market. Instead, there are several established alternatives. The following matrix provides a comparative overview of the different technologies and methods which are currently used. A distinction is made between invasive and non-invasive methods and their degree of preciseness. However, a higher degree of accuracy does not necessarily imply a higher practicability.

Thus, this key point is demonstrated in the size of the bubbles which is directly proportional to the degree of practicability, according to expert opinions.

Figure 12: Comparative overview of different technologies in the fruit quality assurance domain.

Lasers can recognize soft fruits accurately within a few seconds per fruit and are very useful for fruits with a hard skin. However, by cutting into the fruits, they are not sellable anymore and thus produce unnecessary waste (Nakladal, 2019).

Cutting is often used in supermarkets as one step of random quality tests. However, its realization is not practical, as fruits cannot be sold after being cut and go to waste (Wegscheider, 2019).

Expertise includes taste, smell and manual pressure tests of the pickers which is carried out through sample tests very quickly in the fields. As harvesting and quality testing is combined in one single process which is done by low cost manpower, this method is very common among fruit producers, especially in places like Latin- and South America and South Africa (Wernicke, 2019 & Bekker, 2019).

Applying near-infrared hyperspectral imaging (NIR) in fruit sorting and grading processes, a large scale of pieces of fruit can be checked at any time within 1-2 seconds. The technology can read reflections of the waves that come from different kinds of fruits. However, its potential is limited as infrared can only scan the fruit 1-4mm deep. Thus, the core of the fruit cannot be analyzed (Nakladal, 2019).

X-rays detect on density, irrespective of size, moisture or pollution level within 1-5 seconds. Besides, its efficiency, its underlying technological principles do not correspond with emerging trends in the food industry, such as “nature-oriented” or “focus on health” (Nakladal, 2019).

Sorting by parameters like weight, size and colors is a solution for medium to high production rates. Graders measure the weight through load cells in housings. The size is derived from the weight. Colors

are detected through a led lightning system and a high-resolution camera. However, as only the caliber can be determined, problems arise in part of the inner quality (like parasites, impurities, fungus) since this method does not analyze the inner parts of the fruits (Nakladal, 2019).

Fluo technology is used to sort out products which do not contain chlorophyll/solanine or differ in the chlorophyll/solanine level from the good products such as potatoes, peas, green beans, spinach and other leafy products. Time varies depending on the size and density of the fruit and can take up to 10 seconds. The method applies a small amount of mercury liquid which could be harmful for the fruits or vegetables (Nakladal, 2019).

Summing up, NMR spectroscopy competes with technologies and methods that are sufficient in terms of preciseness, speed and usability. Yet there is neither a method nor a technology in the market which is completely non-invasive and delivers all parameters which are necessary to determine a fruit's and vegetable's quality. According to experts there is an increasing demand in 100% non-invasive technologies. Due to its main advantages, which will be discussed in further detail later, NMR spectroscopy would be able to meet the costumers' prospective needs and thus could enter the niche market of 100% non-invasive methods. However, in order to conquer market entry barriers and be competitive, some performance parameters, especially the speed, of NMR have to be improved.

4.3 Customer Discovery

It was identified that the profitability of the technology is limited to certain types of fruits and vegetables. Since the economic affordability of the technology has to be taken into account, the fruit and vegetables will be classified into two categories: Firstly, fruits and vegetables with a higher markup than usual products - meaning the amount added by a merchant to the cost of a product to enable the excess of the break-even point. Mostly tropical fruits like avocados, mangos and pineapples represent fruits with a high markup. They have long transport routes, which cause infections and rottenness. A reduced disposal rate will result in increased product quality and would subsequently boost sales and profits (Kofler, et al., 2017). Secondly, fruits and vegetables with a high sales volume like potatoes, apples and onions enable the amortization of the high investment in the technology. Such high sales volumes enable a reduction in the per unit costs of fruits and vegetables. By making the industry more cost-efficient, a higher profit margin is ensured and, thus, the return of sales can be improved. Consequently, the required fixed costs for the new technology could be covered by increasing a company's contribution margin (Staudigl, 2019).

Customer Groups

In order to identify the targeted customers of a new technology that can be derived from R&D that CERN carries out with superconducting wire and magnet developers, one needs to look into the supply chain of the agricultural market and its different players.

Figure 13: Supply chain in the fruit industry.

Fruit producers crop and harvest their fruits or vegetables. They either sort and grade themselves or outsource this task to sorting and grading companies. Logistics companies deliver the goods to the distributors (mostly supermarkets), who resell them to the end consumers. Since logistic companies only delivery end products and consumers already want to benefit from the high quality once they purchase their goods, these two potential customers will not be looked at in further detail.

Customer Group: Fruit / Vegetable Producer

Figure 14: Customer group analysis of fruit and vegetable producers.

Description

As already mentioned in the previous chapter there are different, established methods and technologies used for the sorting and grading process in order to meet the high-quality guidelines: After harvesting, fruits and vegetables are sorted by a lighting technology, through infrared or even through visual screening. Furthermore, samples are taken for the undergoing of smell and taste tests. “However, the fact that these fruits have been correctly harvested and sorted is still the responsibility of the quality managers who work directly in the field” (Wernicke, 2019). This fact implies that sorting and grading still heavily relies on manual work and know-how transferred by humans, which is passed on from generation to generation. Additionally, creating jobs as part of social corporate responsibility is a core value for multinational companies such as Westfalia, San Lucar and Chiquita (Verborg, 2019). Thus, nowadays, many fruits like mangos and avocados are mostly sorted through pressure tests and vision screenings.

Advantages & Disadvantages

By using the NMR-based technology for sorting and grading processes, fruits and vegetables can be analyzed at an even higher level. For example, infrared currently only allows to check 1-4 mm in depth. Additionally, using x-rays is considered to be contradictory with shared values in the food industry (Nakladal, 2019). Since present technologies cannot determine the degree of ripeness as precisely, the NMR-based technology shows enormous potential. As the level of the preciseness of the sorting and grading process rises, the farmers, producers or intermediaries can resell superior products. Therefore, they experience a higher reputation in the industry.

However, an unfavorable implication for the customer groups occurs due to the high degree of accuracy. There are strict guidelines in the food industry that ensure the quality and reduce the (health) risk for the end consumer. The OECD, for example, recommends explanatory guidelines for international trade on the application of the standards for fruit and vegetables. By the example of potatoes, one guideline constitutes that the potato tuber has to be “intact, i.e. they should not have had any part removed nor have suffered any damage making them incomplete” (OECD, 2009). According to an expert in the potato industry, the higher level of preciseness would actually lead to more waste: “If we used a more precise technology that is able to screen the vegetable down to its core, the throwaway rate rises to about 95% since we would not be able to meet the guidelines anymore” (Heftberger, 2019).

Estimated Potential - *MEDIUM*

Multinational companies appreciate the present technologies and their current scope is sufficed since an upgrade would also be too expensive. “CERN’s technology is very forward looking, but it will hardly be affordable for the broad mass” (Nakladal, 2019). The human know-how is even valued over the potential of sorting technologies. “Sorting machines are quite a hassle..., you can sort it by hand very

easily and it provides reliable information... , no extra machinery involved..., no further hands involved that put the fruits on the sorting machines...” (Bekker, 2019). Furthermore, it is important to mention that the leading share of the disposable quota does not result from infection due to long transport routes but from missing optical standards as well as adverse weather conditions. Heavy unexpected rain, for example, causes a high concentration of bacteria which can no longer be eliminated after the harvest (Wernicke, 2019). Summing up, experts have shown that simplicity and efficiency is the key.

Regarding the degree of ripeness on transport routes, particular circumstances are being created in order to advance or decelerate the ripening process: On the one hand, ethylene is used to boost the ripening process (Wurm, 2019). On the other hand, fruits like apples and bananas can be stored in so-called controlled atmospheres, in which oxygen, carbon dioxide as well as nitrogen are regulated in order to slow down the ripening procedure (Nuster, 2019). Subsequently, most big companies’ throwaway quotas are already very low, since fruits that do not reach the supermarket quality go into other channels. Most of them are utilized by making juice, oil, or even guacamole: “99.9% of the harvested fruits will find its way into trade” (Wernicke, 2019). As waste does not portray an essential issue, a value added of the technology is hard to identify (Verborg, 2019). However, SanLucar, Chiquita and Futura have shown particular interest due to its high potential once the technology is adapted accordingly.

Customer Group: Sorting and Grading Companies

Figure 15: Customer group analysis for fruit and vegetable sorting and grading companies.

Description

Sorting and Grading companies are intermediaries that take over goods from the fruit producers, sort, pack and store them until they are ready to be sold.

Advantages & Disadvantages

Again, sorting and grading companies can analyze their supplied fruits and vegetables at an even higher level.

Yet the question arises what would happen with the fruits that deviate from the premium standard. Due to the strict guidelines which are mentioned above fruits that do not meet the standard will be tossed out and, thus, the disposal rate will increase. Another important factor is that fruits would still have to be cut in order to determine specific parameters such as vitamins, mineral nutrients and aromas. To this day these parameters can only be defined through laboratory testing (Robatscher, 2019).

Estimated Potential - MEDIUM

Methods and technologies such as sorting by caliber and infrared are very common due to their simplicity, speed and routine. However, there is demand in 100% non-invasive technologies that could determine certain parameters which are yet only possible to analyze via invasive methods. One particular company, namely Kröpfl Obsthandel GesmbH, showed interest in the technology. Since this customer group shows the highest potential among all customer groups further in-depth research is strongly recommended.

Customer Group: Distributors

Figure 16: Customer group analysis for fruit and vegetable distributors.

Description

About 10% of fruits and vegetables are verified by supermarkets before distribution. Since incoming deliveries in supermarkets go on sale the same day, the sorting has to be carried out quickly and efficiently. Therefore, the supermarket only checks its deliveries through random tests conducted by quality officers using simple methods like by color schemes or grading by size and weight (Wegscheider, 2019). The success of the verification of the fruit and vegetable quality, therefore, rather relies on management skills, human resources and expert knowledge than on the performance of precisely-working grading technologies. The main success factor for ensuring high quality is the short time between delivery entrance and display in the supermarket shelves (Wegscheider, 2019).

In general, switching costs refer to the costs that a consumer has to bear as a result of changing brands, suppliers, or products. In grocery shopping, the switching costs refer to the costs that occur when a

consumer decides to shop at another supermarket than usual. Especially in urban areas, several supermarket chains are represented frequently. Nevertheless, in order to ensure customer loyalty, most supermarkets introduce individual loyalty programs (Wegscheider, 2019). Additionally, they must provide the highest possible quality: “If we deliver spoiled fruits or vegetables, we bear the risks and costs.” (Wegscheider, 2019).

Advantages & Disadvantages

Using the NMR-based technology to sort fruits and vegetables would increase the quality because also inner damages would be detected that might have occurred during transportation and storage. Only fruits and vegetables that meet the internal supermarket guidelines end up on sale. By using the precise technology to analyze fruits and vegetables, the selection of suppliers could be optimized. Moreover, suppliers whose quality is not as superior as others would be replaced. By optimizing the quality of its products, the supermarket would benefit from a higher reputation and customer satisfaction and thus, it would be able to tie its customers to its company (Wegscheider, 2019).

Nonetheless, as the performance of the fruit and vegetable sorting and grading technology leads to the detection of defects in fruits and vegetables, the disposal rate would increase. Countries have different legal regulations dealing with waste. In France and Belgium, for example, supermarkets are legally obliged to donate non-sold food (ORF, 2015). Vice versa, the higher disposal rate leads to a decrease in sales. However, the investment in the technology should - in the best case - be covered through more sales which are crucial for the amortization of the high investment in the technology. Moreover, in addition to the investment, the supermarket would still bear the burden of payment as it buys fruits and vegetables from suppliers which are then classified as spoiled and thus not sellable.

Estimated Potential - LOW

As already mentioned above, once the fruits and vegetables are obtained from their suppliers, they immediately have to be distributed to the shelves in the supermarkets. Therefore, time plays a very significant role. Since the use of NMR spectroscopy can take up to a couple of minutes per fruit, this constraint cannot be easily met. Additionally, each fruit supplier might portray different expertise in their produced fruits. Therefore, supermarkets cannot acquire this complete knowledge and cannot guarantee and create optimal storage conditions for their variety of products: “Supermarkets do not have the right capacities and infrastructure for sorting and grading on a large scale – we have to rely on our suppliers and their expertise” (Wegscheider, 2019). Therefore, there is no demand for NMR spectroscopy for distributors.

4.4 Value Estimation

The following graph depicts the values of the technology, which were estimated by regional as well as multinational fruit producers, distributors and sorting companies in order to assure a diverse set of opinions. A brief description of the companies is given in the appendix. One can clearly see that the technology's value is rated far lower than its actual price (1.5 million euro), which indicates a low value estimation and, therefore, a low willingness to pay. Thus, research & development, as well as production costs, would have to be reduced considerably in order to be attractive for the broad mass. Additionally, different factors (which are explained in the recommendation section) have to be optimized in order to increase the value for the industry.

Figure 17: Value estimation of the technology.

However, it is important to mention that the application of this radical and innovative technology would lead to a major change in the industry. Thus, one has to bear in mind that the rejection of the experts contacted possibly results from psychological factors such as fear of change and economic factors like redundancies or the devaluation of existing know-how (Franke, 2018). Since this refusal constitutes an obstacle, the potential customer groups have to be prepared and their mindset has to be adapted in such a way that new concepts are accepted in a contemporary way.

4.5 Further Potential Application Fields

In-Ovo Sexing of Chicken Eggs to Prevent Chick Culling

Further research has shown that the application of NMR Spectroscopy in the poultry industry, especially the broiler industry, seems to be promising (Feng, Zhang, Ye, & Liu, 2007). The poultry industry is the biggest meat industry with more than 117 million tons of meat consumed per year, and still growing, as the poultry meat consumption is estimated to reach 129 million tons per year by 2021. The poultry industry, thus, accounts for 38.8% of the entire meat industry (Statista, 2018). In the EU27 alone, the poultry industry had an output of 12.9 million tons in 2012, whereas broilers represented and still represent the largest proportion, accounting for three quarters of all poultry kept. In 2017 the poultry meat production has risen by 10.5% compared to 2010. Furthermore, the poultry production industry's value was 24.6 bn in 2012 in the EU27 alone (LEI Wageningen UR, 2013).

Figure 18: Meat consumption by type in Europe.

NMR-spectroscopy could address the so-called chick culling problem, the killing of male chickens right after hatching. The food industry does not want to fatten male chicks due to less economic value in comparison to hens. In order to save the costs of the expensive rearing of the rooster, they are suffocated or shredded immediately after hatching (Iser & Stockrahm, 2019). In 2017 alone, 45 mn male chicks were killed in Germany – the worldwide number is estimated to be somewhere between four and six bn culled chicks – and this number does not seem to be diminishing (Springmann, 2019; Iser & Stockrahm, 2019; Matthews, 2019). By using NMR-Spectroscopy the chicken's sex could be determined in the egg and the killing prevented (Springmann, 2019).

Currently, this issue is of particular relevance, as animal welfare activists are suing hatcheries that practice chick culling, as it is a violation of the Animal Welfare Act (of most western countries), which prohibits an animal from being inflicted physical pain or killed without good reason (Bund Österreich,

2019; Bundesamt für Justiz, n.d.). Hatcheries are also looking for other, more practical solutions, where neither an economic burden, such as raising and fattening roosters or the persistent threat of lawsuits, nor an ethical burden, such as chick culling, negatively impact their business. By in-ovo sexing, all of the above-mentioned problems could be solved. Furthermore, the already fertilized, non-hatched eggs could be sold as they are undamaged. They could be used in the production of pet-food-production or used in the research for immunomedical research, since several vaccines (especially flu shots) are egg-based (Matthews, 2019; Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, 2018).

There are already practices, such as the “Seleggt method”, in which a hole is made in the shell and an endocrinological procedure is used to test a drop of allantois-fluid for certain hormones and determining the sex (Spektrum, 2019; Seleggt, 2019). However, this can still cause problems, as invasive in-ovo sexing can only be performed in a very late stage of the growth process, which again results in animal welfare concerns (Iser & Stockrahm, 2019). With the technique of NMR spectroscopy, the determination of the sex in the egg should be able to be performed early and non-invasively (Kosse, 2019). The scanning process could be used to infer the size of chromosomes or to identify gender-specific characteristics in the egg at a very early stage of hatching (Lossau, 2018). Initial expert opinions suggest the feasibility of the method but assume that the scans would take a long time. Although work is already underway on these scans, there is still considerable potential for improvement regarding the scanning time (Kosse, 2019).

Quality Control of Vanilla

From a technological perspective, NMR spectroscopy can also be applied in the quality control process of vanilla, an agricultural product with very high market value. In the following, market characteristics, regulations and the supply chain of the vanilla industry are described.

European vanilla imports are declining due to worldwide vanilla shortage and rising global prices. Imports from developing countries represent a value of 394 million euro per year. France, Germany and the Netherlands are the top three importers of vanilla. In 2017, the top exporters of vanilla were Madagascar (MUSD 894), Indonesia (MUSD 132), Germany (MUSD 47), France (MUSD 46.3) and Canada (MUSD 36.2) (OEC, 2017). Product quality is always the key issue. Products need to comply with the European Spice Association (ESA) or with the American Spice Trade Association (ASTA). In 2018¹, the vanilla price per kg amounted to USD 527.27 and with peaks up to USD 700, compared to USD 40 in 2011. It's market value is higher than that of silver which amounted to USD 515 (Pilling, 2018). Especially exporters have to comply with legally building requirements: maximum levels of

¹ <https://www.ft.com/content/02042190-65bc-11e8-90c2-9563a0613e56>

mycotoxins, maximum residue levels of pesticides, microbiological contamination, food additives, adulteration, maximum levels of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons and irradiation (CBI Ministry of Foreign Affairs, n.d.).

The supply chain in the vanilla industry looks as follows:

Figure 19: Supply chain of the Vanilla industry.

Major problems of the vanilla market are uncertainties and fluctuation. In 2017, the vanilla crisis accelerated: food and beverage companies are challenged with supply concerns, fluctuating pricing and shifting quality. Changing weather conditions due to global warming are leading to late flowering of vanilla, decreasing the quality of the crop. Moreover, suppliers are forecasting decreases in production and a reduction in quality. However, customers demand higher quality.

An NMR spectroscopy appliance, tailored for the specific application, could be used for ensuring the quality in accordance with the legal guidelines. Therefore, exporters (as shown in the value chain) represent potential customers. However, the willingness to pay and the demand in such a technology have to be discovered first in order to assess the potential of this use case.

5 Strategic Recommendations

Based on the analyses, strategic recommendations are given for both scrap metal recycling and fruit sorting. For scrap metal recycling, four specific actions are recommended, whereas the recommendations for fruit sorting and grading are focusing on the optimization of each performance indicator.

5.1 Scrap Metal Recycling

Four crucial pillars should guide CERN's future course of action in the scrap metal recycling industry.

On the **short-term horizon**, CERN should **focus on the exploitation of the industry which currently holds the most potential** for the technology. Currently, the **aluminum recycling industry profits most** from the furnace's use benefits. Especially the **use of electricity instead of gas** is of high relevance within the industry (Antrekowitsch & Scheele, 2019) for economic and ecological optimisation reasons.

On the **mid-term horizon**, **increasing the furnaces maximum temperature** is essential. Currently, the furnace is limited to a temperature of around 900 °C. However, the furnace's use **benefits unfold their greatest potential in recycling industries that need higher temperatures, such as using the technology to separate precious metals** melting at least 961°C. Furthermore, the furnace would gain in competitiveness if the **heating speed** could be increased since current technologies' heating pace is faster than 50 K per hour (Duspiva, Ek, Scheele, Antrekowitsch, & Hoffmann, 2019). Therefore, R&D for the adaption of the technology is a crucial cornerstone regarding the future relevance of the technology.

Once the technology adaption has been successfully implemented, in the **long-term CERN should enter co-innovation projects the precious metals recycling market** since the furnaces use benefits are the most effective and relevant within this particular industry (Löbbus, Bartley, & Antrekowitsch, 2019). Especially, the use of argon as a protective gas as well as the higher preciseness of the temperature regulation enable recycling companies to reduce the loss of material due to oxidation.

Lastly, CERN should also engage in the market-oriented exploration of further application fields. For example, heat treatment has been identified as a major field of interest due to the relevance of the furnace's features (Kopils , Antrekowitsch, & Ohnweiler, 2019). A potential application field could be the aerospace industry since certain parts need special heat-treatment in order to endure the forces acting upon them (Ohnweiler, 2019).

Figure 20: Use benefit assessment of heat treatment.

5.2 Fruit Sorting and Grading

“Fruit producers will be most likely to purchase a **NMR spectroscopy based appliance if the high investment pays off**. Therefore, one should be able to **determine additional quality parameters and increase the technology’s speed**.” (Robatscher, 2019).

Given that researchers want to introduce NMR spectroscopy to the fruit sorting and grading market, the **performance of some technology parameters needs to be increased**. The hexagon down below depicts the current degree of different parameters of NMR spectroscopy which should be taken into account when looking into its improvement and potential.

In terms of preciseness and the relevance in the future, no further adaptations will be necessary due to the fact that **this technology promises already a more accurate determination than technologies that already exist on the market**. However, it is **crucial to increase its speed**. Adjusting it to the same level of speed as NIR would immensely increase its potential.

Figure 21 Technology Attractiveness Hexagon

In terms of costs **the technology has to be affordable for the broad mass** and its **benefits must significantly exceed its costs**. Furthermore, its usability should be extended to attract further customers. For example, there is a demand in quality measurement instruments that can be used directly in the field. Thus, the degree of ripeness of non-climacteric fruits could be determined before even being harvested. Lastly, the **number of detectable parameters (for example vitamins, mineral nutrients and aromas) should be extended**, increasing the technology's demand by making it 100% non-invasive. This is an inter-sectoral R&D topic, not related to the NMR technology, but to the analysis algorithms and software infrastructure. Apart from increasing the performance of NMR spectroscopy, CERN should **look into further promising niche application fields** which were discovered in this project: Both **in-ovo sexing of chicken eggs and the analysis of the quality of vanilla** seem to be profitable application fields. However, the degree of its potential and possible required adjustments need to be examined further.

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Appendix

Key Players Scrap Metal Recycling

This section lists some of the most relevant providers of the recycling technology in that field most as well as key players in the aluminum recycling industry. Both groups could be highly relevant partners in the future and interested in the improvement of their technologies.

Furnace Manufacturers

Andritz AG

Andritz produces and assembles components for about 90 different products for the Hydro, Pulp & Paper, Separation, and Metals business areas, and also carries out repair, rebuild and field installation work.

The business area Andritz Metals (former "Rolling Mills and Strip Processing") is the third largest business unit Andritz employs over 30,000 people. In 2018, the company's turnover amounted to EUR 6.03 bn; in 2017, it was EUR 5.89 bn, which is an increase of 2.38%.

OTTO JUNKER GmbH

Otto Junker GmbH is a global leader in the manufacture of complex industrial furnace systems and is also active in the stainless-steel foundry. The company has a yearly turnover of around EUR 150 mn.

Inductotherm Group

Inductotherm Group leads the industry in the development and manufacturing of advanced technologies, products and systems for the heat-driven transformation of metals and specialty materials.

Striko Westofen

StrikoWestofen is a global manufacturer of thermal processing technology for the light metal casting industry and provides energy-efficient solutions for die-casting, gravity casting, sand casting and low-pressure casting.

Recycling Companies

Aurubis AG

Aurubis is a leading worldwide provider of non-ferrous metals. The company processes complex metal concentrates and diverse recycling raw materials. Aurubis is the global leader for copper recycling. In 2018, the company's turnover amounted to EUR 10.424; in 2017 it was EUR 9.880bn, which is an increase of 5.51%.

Umicore NV/SA

Umicore is a global materials technology and recycling group with about 10,400. Umicore generates the majority of its revenues and dedicates most of its R&D efforts to clean technologies, such as emission control catalysts, materials for rechargeable batteries and recycling. Umicore's overriding goal of sustainable value creation is based on an ambition to develop, produce and recycle materials in a way that fulfils its mission: materials for a better life. In 2018, the company's turnover amounted to EUR 13.71 bn; in 2017 it was EUR 11.95 bn, which is an increase of 14.73%.

Boliden AB

Boliden is a high-tech metal company with its own mines and smelters that work over the long term to guarantee society's supply of base metals and precious metals through the mining of ore (minerals) and the production and delivery of high-quality metals to industry. In 2018, the company's turnover amounted to EUR 5.25 bn; in 2017 it was EUR 4.95 bn, which is an increase of 6.06%.

Metallo Belgium N.V.

Metallo N.V. provides non-ferrous multi-metal recycling and refining services. The company offers smelting, converting, distillation, and electrolysis services. It produces metals, such as copper, tin, lead, nickel, tankhouse slimes, zinc oxide, and metamix. Metallo Belgium N.V. was formerly known as Metallo-Chimique N.V.

AMAG Austria Metall AG

AMAG Austria Metall AG is a supplier of primary aluminum and premium cast and rolled aluminum products. At the integrated site in Ranshofen, Austria the company fully leverages its core competencies in recycling, casting, rolling, heat-treatment, and surface finishing. With a 75-80 % share of scrap in the raw material mix AMAG sets the industry benchmark regarding recycling. In 2018, the company's turnover amounted to EUR 1.10 bn; in 2017 it was EUR 1.03 bn, which is an increase of 6.80%.

Norsk Hydro ASA

Hydro is a fully integrated aluminum company with 35,000 employees in 40 countries on all continents, combining local expertise, worldwide reach and unmatched capabilities in R&D. In addition to production of primary aluminum, rolled and extruded products and recycling, Hydro also extracts bauxite, refines alumina and generates energy to be the only 360° company of the global aluminum industry. In 2018, the company's turnover amounted to EUR 15.94 bn; in 2017 it was EUR 10.92 bn, which is an increase of 45.97%.

Slovalco a.s.

Slovalco is primary aluminum producer. Our final products are aluminum alloys in the shape of extrusion ingots and primary foundry alloys shaped as ingots. Aluminum products are further processing in other industries (automotive, aircraft, electro-technical, construction etc.). In 2018, the company's turnover amounted to EUR 475.797 mn; in 2017, it was EUR 416.380 mn, which is an increase of 14.27%.

Real Alloy

Real Alloy is the global market leader in third-party aluminum recycling and specification alloy production. The company converts aluminum scrap and by-products into reusable aluminum metal for a growing number of applications across various industries.

Trimet

As an innovative, medium-sized, family-owned company, Trimet develops, produces, recycles, casts, and sells modern light-metal products made of aluminum at eight locations. The company currently employs around 3,200 employees.

Alusigma S.A.

Alusigma S.A. is a company from Asturias (north of Spain), whose production began in 2004 in its new facilities in Somonte (Gijon), where the company produces aluminum alloys for the automotive industry and, in addition, aluminum used in steel deoxidation. Alusigma S.A. annually recycles more than 26,000 tons of aluminum subproducts and other residues (copper scraps, magnesium, foams, etc.).

Company Descriptions Fruit Sorting and Grading

San Lucar Austria

San Lucar is a multinational firm in the supply of all kinds of fruits and vegetables. Within 30 nations it employs 2800 people who are contributing to getting about 500,000 kilos of fresh fruits and vegetables from 35 growing countries worldwide into the shopping baskets every day.

In 2018, the company's turnover amounted to EUR 400 mn; in 2017 EUR 380 mn.

Giovanelli Fruchimport AG

Giovanelli is a leading Swiss company which imports fruits, vegetables, berries and mushrooms from all over the world.

Westfalia Fruit

Westfalia is a multinational leader in the supply of subtropical fruits such as avocados and mangoes. Its sales offices range from Europe to North- and South America and to South Africa. It has the largest avocado-growing footprint in the world. Westfalia has multiple subsidiaries in different countries. For example, Greencell, a company in England which manages over 100,000 tons of fruit per year. Westfalia Fruit is also the largest exporter of South African avocados, mainly to European markets. It has recently launched the biggest Hass avocado processing plant in Columbia. In 2018, the company's turnover amounted to EUR 13,6 mn; in 2016 its profits after tax amounted to EUR 9,2 mn.

EFKO

EFKO is an international company with subsidiaries in Austria and the Czech Republic. EFKO produces more than 110,000 tons preserves every year. It stores and trades 4,200 tons of apples every year.

Prenner Beerenkultur

Prenner Beerenkultur is a family owned business in Marchfeld, Austria. They grow and harvest fruits and berries.

ARDO Frost

ARDO Frost is a worldwide expert who delivers fruits and vegetables to over 100 countries and has a sales volume of about 860,000 tones per year.

In 2017, the company's turnover amounted to EUR 1 bn.

Commercial Fruit Growers Styria

Commercial fruit growers in Styria is an association for exporting fruits to Europe and the Middle East.

Frutura GmbH

Frutura GmbH is a subsidiary of DOL Dörrobstland Vertriebs GmbH, which operates internationally. Its facilities include a packing house, including one of the most modern banana ripening facilities in Europe, a fresh food logistics company. Around 40 countries are among the partners of Frutura. By now, the international production and marketing program encompasses 4,500 items.

METRO

METRO is an international distributor and wholesaler which supplies the catering sector and also the end customer.

Chiquita Brands International Sarl (CBIS)

Chiquita is a multinational company and is a core supplier of bananas but also distributes pineapples. In 2015, its turnover amounted to EUR 3.014 bn.

Interview Notes

The following register will follow this structure:

Name	Company	Profession	Date Location	Type	Interview Participant	Language
Key insights and interview notes						

Furthermore, following abbreviations are valid in this register to improve the readability of the tables.

Abbreviation	Name
BL	Brzobohaty Leonie
HS	Habernig Sebastian
MPe	Moravec Peter
PMi	Pably Michael
ST	Schürz Theresa

Johannes Gutleber	CERN	Project partner	19/03/19 WU	e-mail	PMi	GER
Introduction of the team; clarification of the precise tasks of scrap metal recycling and fruit sorting						

Timm Ohnweiler	Carbolite Gero	Technical director	07/03/19 WU	Phone	BL, HS, MPe, PMi, ST	GER
Detailed description of the technology (= furnace). Explanation of its potential.						

Franz Brändl	Bezirksbauern- kammer NÖ	Manager	27/03/19 WU	Phone	BL, ST	GER
Provided further contact: Karl Auer (Auer Gartenbau)						

Rochus Nepf	Ardo Austria Frost GmbH	Head of quality management	01/04/19 WU	Phone	PMi	GER
Ardo Austria Frost produces vegetables like carrots, pumpkins, spinach, red and white cabbage and soybeans. They use a camera-sorting-machine which only check the vegetables for damages on the surface. A sorting machine which can determine the ripeness of the fruits is not necessary for them, since the maximum delivery time is about twelve hours. Nonetheless, they think a sorting machine which uses NMRs could be useful to vet the harvested vegetables for insects and other foreign objects like leaves, stems and dirt.						

Martina Zillinger	Niederösterreich ischer Gemüsebauverb and	Supplier	26/03/19 WU	Phone	PMi	GER
Martina Zillinger is a supplier for the local vegetable industry with a focus on potatoes. She outsources the sorting process, by selling the harvest unsorted to LGV Frischgemüse Wien regGesmbh, a packaging and sorting company. She thinks a NMR sorting machine has huge potential on not only the regional but also global market. Further contact information was gathered.						

Karl Auer	Auer Gartenbau	Owner and manager	03/04/19 WU	Phone	PMi	GER
Karl Auer is the owner and manager of Auer-Gartenbau. His production focus lies on broccoli (1 million units per year), cabbages, spinach and lettuce. He performs the sorting process in his own company. For broccoli, there is an own sorting circuit, which separates the broccoli based on their weight. The quality analysis is a manual process. Furthermore, he thinks that the NMR-based sorting process has enormous potential for other fruit-formed vegetables and fruits. Further contacts: Josef Beck; LGV						

Marion Palka-Kaltenbrunner	Unternehmensb eratung	Manager	19/03/19 WU	e-mail	PMi	GER
Mag. Marion Palka-Kaltenbrunner was contacted and introduced to both tasks. She will provide more contacts for both projects.						

Hubert Zatschkowitsch	Zatschkowitsch GmbH	Owner	30/03/19 Vienna	Personal	PMi	GER
Mr. Zatschkowitsch thinks that the NMR-based grading process could find application in the onion production to determine internal damages. As an example, he mentioned that onions, which are damaged by hail while they grow, build new layers around the damaged core. This makes the onion look undamaged from the outside but already rots on the inside. A more extended interview will follow, as well as contacts Mr. Zatschkowitsch is willing to provide.						

Scholz	Scholz Recycling GmbH	Owner	02/04/19 WU	Phone	BL, HS	EN
Scholz AG no longer exists. Now Scholz Recycling GmbH. Collects scrap metal and passes it on to foundries. Scholz GmbH is intermediary. Subsidiary (recycle cars, separate metals).						

Stephan Winder	AMR Austrian Metal Recovery GmbH	Manager	11/04/19 WU	Phone	BL, HS	GER
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Scrap-metal recycling, head of controlling. Discussed the relevance of the furnaces features.						
Reinhard Heinzlmann	AMR Austrian Metal Recovery GmbH	Manager	11/04/19 WU	Phone	BL, HS	GER
Customers include the metalworking industry. Changed position 3 months ago. New contact person: Mr. Stephan Winder, Slag is produced from waste, separated, iron and non-ferrous metals are recovered. Non-ferrous metals: copper, lead, tin, aluminum, zinc. Mixture not 100% pure, goes on to recyclers in Austria, Germany, Holland, Italy. Refine material and return it to the cycle. Currently how separated? By dry process. Ferrous and non-ferrous separators; plant crushes, conditioners, separators separate. Several separators, series of process steps. Screened, different fractions are produced (stones, glass, metals, etc.)						
Günther Höggerl	Müller-Guttenbrunn Group	Manager	11/04/19 WU	Phone	BL, HS	GER
Company description: The Müller-Guttenbrunn Group is a recycling company whose focus is on the following fractions: end-of-life vehicles (ELV), electrical and electronic scrap (WEEE), Mixed metals and plastic. Mission: Continuous development and expansion is ensured by constant observation of the market and key parameters. Sound knowledge and the best available technology, together with a lean corporate structure, form the basis for efficient and effective recycling in order to return material to the production cycle.						
Günther Höggerl	Müller-Guttenbrunn Group	Manager	23/04/19 WU	Phone	BL, HS	GER
Mr. Günther Höggerl is in charge of the R&D department of the Müller-Guttenbrunn Group. In the interview, he rigorously described their current recycling process, going into particular detail in their Automotive recycling process. He explained that the recycling of cars will face various difficulties in a furnace with only one process step and that the current process is already very efficient. The main problems that arise applying the heat based-separation method are that the materials first would have to find their way out of the compound when melted and the limited reliability on the full protection of corrosion with the protective gas Argon. He further explained the current value-chain of the recycling industry.						
Sebastian Skole	ARDO Frost	Purchase manager	15/04/19 WU	Phone	PMi, ST	GER
ARDO controls and sorts by itself using manual and optical (camera) sorting processes. The sorting system comes from Sortex and sorts by color and shape. The biggest problems in the sorting process are the detection of fineness's (quality classes) and the differentiation of foreign material from the fruit, especially when the color and shape are the same as the actual fruit (e.g. toxic weeds → "Nachtschatten"). The transport does not really play a role when it comes to ripeness, as the vegetables are immediately frozen after sorting. The transport to the sorting stage is so short that it does not cause any problems. The cost of the new technology has been estimated at between EUR 250,000 and EUR 400,000. Passing on contacts: Ecuador: Probe fruit, Serbia: Friglo, Elixier fruits; Poland: numerous companies but for example orscof food						
Willibald Nuster	Erzeugerorganisation der Erwerbsobstbauern Steiermark	Quality manager	15/04/19 WU	Phone	PMi, ST	GER
Sorting is carried out mechanically with a camera via Grevia and Stas. The apples are measured and the stem axis and color are inspected. Errors are eliminated. Around 60 photos are taken per apple and the external condition is inspected. Since the fruit is inhomogeneous, the data from earlier sorting tests such as scans using infrared methods are not usable. It would be interesting to measure density and sugar content (as starch → sugar → maturity level). Transport: The apple is harvested and stored in CA storage (Controlled Atmosphere) for up to one year and removed as required. It is sold all the way to the United Arab Emirates; Egypt - sometimes directly via refrigerated containers with CA or sometimes in normal containers (depending on whether the customer pays for what has been agreed or how "premium" the product is). Reasons for waste are overripening, damage to the fruit itself due to fallen fruit, pests, fungal diseases (storage scab). The cost of the new technology has been estimated at around EUR 100,000. Interest would be very high - but at the moment there is little budget due to strong competition. Further important insights: The technology could be used for meat and sausage products because it is a homogeneous mass. Opportunity costs CA Warehousing <-> Sorting according to degree of maturity? Further contacts: Frutura GmbH - Banana ripening, logistics for SPAR, Kröpfl fruit trade						
Andreas Staudigl	EZB Bauern Erdäpfel Verkaufs GmbH	Intermediary for production	15/04/19 WU	Phone	PMi, ST	GER
His company does not make the packaging itself but sells only unsorted goods - passing on contacts: Strobl in Suttentbrunn, Lapro in Stockerau, Dorfinger, Rupp in Labendorf, Bauer Viendorf/ Göllersdorf -> among others the biggest packers (potato and onion) Goods warmed up and sorted and washed, sorted according to variety and cooking characteristics						
Alexander Jecha	Eduard und Johann Strobl GmbH	Purchase + sale	15/04/19 WU	Phone	PMi, ST	GER
Useful hints: It is better to ask the production companies than the traders themselves (further contact: Christian Strobl at Hollabrunn) Trading companies are one step too late in the chain (they have no influence on the quality anymore) -> important to get in touch with the initial producers from countries of origin such as Spain, Greece ask. For stone fruits, processes already exist, which give information without having to pierce the fruit - such as the printing method, which analyzes internal values. Quality is expected for pre-matured products. However, this would only be affordable due to a high quantity and high price items - otherwise the costs would be too high.Mr.						

Jecha could imagine great interest in potatoes, since they are often only looked at from the outside -> but when the customers peel the potatoes “ they find it in a quality they sometimes don't expect”. Shelf life plays less of a role with potatoes, as customers want to buy pre-matured products.

Fam. Sigmund	Prenner Beerenkultur	Management	15/04/19 WU	Phone	PMi, ST	GER
Further contact information: Rainer Sigmund, Prenner Beerenkultur						

Rainer Sigmund	Prenner Beerenkultur	Management	15/04/19 WU	Phone	PMi, ST	GER
<p>Prenner Beerenkultur processes raspberries, blueberries and blackberries. In general, berries can only be sorted in the field and manually since a machine would crush the berries. Blueberries might work, but the machine would be too expensive for a small business and might not be commercially viable.</p> <p>Another problem is that berries do not ripen after picking, so sorting has to be done in the field before harvesting. Furthermore, the transport distance is very short and takes place within a radius of 50km.</p> <p>There would be interest, for example, in the mechanical sorting of blueberries regarding the quality class as well as in the recognition of the degree of ripeness directly in the field -> Just because blackberries already appear physically ripe does not mean that they already are.</p> <p>hint: There might be interest for tomatoes</p>						

Franz Duspiva	ATM Recyclingssysteme GmbH	Head of sales	24/04/19 WU	Phone	HS	GER
<p>Ing. Duspiva Franz is the head of sales at ATM Recycling systems GmbH. The firm is a major producer of recycling technologies and clients like Volvo, Skoda, Jaguar, Daimler Benz. In the first step, he explained the business model and the value chain of the industry. He then voiced concerns about the envisaged usage of the technology for their business. He pointed out that, recycled materials, in general, have to meet specific criteria after the recycling process. Notably, the remainder of other materials included the end product is highly crucial and that this cannot be prevented. Melting, for example, cars which include a highly diverse amount of materials would make it highly intricate to achieve the right compositions of materials in the end products. Therefore, a certain pre-selection of materials before the smelting would be a necessity. Furthermore, he pointed out that argon is used in almost every modern furnace to protect the metals from corrosion and also provided some alternatives. Moreover, he explained that in the aluminum industry bigger furnaces are used, holding up as much as 30000 l. Due to the high cost of such machinery, he pointed out that only big companies are willing and able to buy such machinery. Additionally, he provided information concerning the costs of switching to new technology and the current threat of new technologies on the market. These were both described as rather low due to the quick amortization of recycling machines (especially when recycling expensive metals) and the shift of focus on the analyses of the materials rather the recycling technology itself. The concentration of producers was described as rather low with only several producers in Europe. Generally, he described the market as stagnating since a lot of the recycling is outsourced to Asia. Lastly, he told us the price of a standard machine and the price spectrum of his product range.</p>						

Andrejs Kopils	LekonGermess Ltd	Business development director	24/04/19 WU	Phone	HS	EN
<p>Andrejs Kopils is the business development director of LekonGermess Ltd seated in Riga. The company is specializing in metal recovery and recycling, production of alloys and process engineering. In order to melt their materials, they need a temperature of at least 1500 degrees. This temperature cannot be achieved by the furnace of CERN and therefore would not fit their business model and additionally would be too expensive for them. Mr. Kopils described their current recycling process and that they heat their materials with electricity which is inducted through electric rods and added that it is not nearly as precise as the technology of CERN. He explained that the company separates the materials using the density differences of the materials and added that separation through heat would not provide a good quality separation. Furthermore, they explained that they only use an furnace to separate small samples. Mainly big aluminum companies could be of interest according to him, even though some technology adaptations would be required. Furthermore, he added that it needs to be clear how the molten aluminum escapes the furnace once its molten. Moreover, he suggested some use cases. Firstly, it could be used to stiffen certain materials through heat-treatment. Another field could be electronic scrap, but the emergence of toxic fumes would be a downside. Furthermore, he pointed out that the main advantage of the furnace is its size. They said that the overall industry and recycling rate is growing, but the profitability is to some extent depending on the prices of the raw materials.</p>						

Anonymus	Sims Recycling Solutions	-	24/04/19 WU	Phone	HS	GER
<p>An expert in the field of the recycling of electronic scrap (Printed circuit boards, keyboards) first described us their current recycling process which is purely mechanical and physical. After their process, their scrap is shipped to smelters and then returned into the industry. Moreover, she pointed out that combining these steps into one process through a heat-based separation is highly impractical for electronic waste since the materials are not very homogenous enough in their composition. Therefore, it is hard to imagine that the end product generated meets the desired quality criteria. Finally, the expert emphasized that the market for electronic scrap only consists of four recyclers in Austria which all lack the financial resources to buy such a technology.</p>						

Ross Bartley	Bureau of International Recycling (BIR)	Trade & Environment Director	24/04/19 WU	Phone	HS	EN
<p>Ross Bartley acts as the Trade & Environment Director of the Bureau of International Recycling (BIR). The BIR is a global recycling industry association representing more than 700 companies from the private sector and 40 national trade federations from 70 different countries. He explained the general value-chain of the scrap recycling industry. According to Mr. Bartley, the European scrap metal recycling industry is pyramid shaped with around 20000 companies. The majority being small & middle-sized firms and about 300 multinationals. Furthermore, he pointed out that the majority of the large volume, small margin business big multinationals engage in recycling aluminum, steel, and copper. There is no lack of thermal-treatment facilities according to Mr. Bartley, and especially big companies often have their own furnaces. The recycling of rarer elements, on the other hand, is something that grows in importance, but</p>						

the amount of companies specializing in that area is a lot smaller. Moreover, he described that differential melting should only be performed at the lowest end of the recycling process. A lack of proper pre-selection could harm the environment and would only provide a very crude and low-quality outcome. Additionally, he pointed out that recycling electronic waste via heat-based separation has been tried, but has not taken off commercially and, therefore, a high probability of being unprofitable. As a potential application field, he named the recovery of carbon fiber due to the need precise temperature control to prevent damage of the fiber.

Andre Martinuzzi	Institute for Ecological Economies WU Vienna	Professor	23/04/19 WU	Phone	ST	GER
Further contact: NTU Athens						

Jose Parejo	Fairtrasa Holland BV	Operating Manager	26/04/19 WU	Phone	PMi, ST	EN
Fruits is sort out in country of origin by suppliers. At arrival sometimes they repack fruit and it is done by an external company.						

Georg Wernicke	San Lucar Austria	Marketing management austria	29/04/19 WU	Phone	BL, PMi	GER
<p>NMR technology unknown. It would be relevant if a contract is necessary? Maintenance? Fundamental attitude of the company: People in the center, because people have the most intuition. They sort it themselves; outsourcing does not work.</p> <p>Fruit industry: the sorting process still happens in the field by workers (manpower).</p> <p>San Lucar sorting system: superficial quality guidelines directly in the field (by sorting out). Varies according to fruit. From/on the ground, for example melons, no bacterial contamination in further storage/transport, washed, sorted by size, by scanner (lighting technology or infrared), guided in different lanes, classified by size/caliber. However, the fact that this fruit has been harvested is still the responsibility of the quality managers in the field directly (e.g. the fruit is pricked). Also taste test a small test.</p> <p>Downstream sorting process: size, caliber of fruit. 98% of all cases are suitable for the further process.</p> <p>Example grapes: natural wax layer on the fruits, umbel only needs to be cut off, then packed in paper bags, comes in directly and then in the post-sorting process only optimum weight sorted out and washed. Then back into these bags. Categorisation of the fruit:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Berries harvested ripened to the point, as quickly as possible in the trade - More than 95% different varieties regularly on the market - Local growing areas for berries in Austria but also overseas in other seasons, these transports are strongly supported by digital technology, optimal atmosphere is created during transport (by logistics partner), 2-3 weeks on the container ship, logged, live on screen, container must maintain optimal temperature - New technical CO₂ reduced atmosphere as alternative to temperature method for transport, also has positive effect for non-ripening fruits - Apples for European market from Germany and Austria - Bananas are the most popular fruits in Austria, San Lucar's hobbyhorse, Ecuador's own ways, interaction of how I grow and harvest frequencies, margin → to bring as much as possible to market in competition, soil is leached out, too much sunlight etc. broken. Soil dead after a few years due to monoculture. Not sustainable. In harmony with nature is motto of SL, most valuable good = employees. Potential for the group, for worldwide growing groups, somewhat difficult, because brand product under the brand SL built on the two pillars human is important. The more technology - perhaps cheaper, but why is San Lucar more expensive? not so that fruit is visually more beautiful, but more expensive because more use is made of the individual product (also financially). Pride in it, because of motto in harmony with man and nature, more technology would not be so compatible with brand image. GLOBAL2000 close cooperation. San Lucar sees little potential in the use of CERN technology. Please keep up to date with what comes out of the project, forward to quality management in Spain - then you are really interested, then get in touch. San Lucar is not a green label, no certificates, but hand in fire: there are many companies that are certified organic, but the bubble is sure to burst in the near future. High rate of throwaway in the trade because fruits do not meet the optical standards. SL disposable quota: per week Germany plus Austria: just over 0.1% disposable quota. juices and smoothies have also been in the range since 2016. That's why "ugly" fruits are also processed into juice. But the quota will certainly fall even further. Disposable quota due to natural "catastrophes" main share quota. For example: Spain's strawberry growing region, then heavy unexpected rain, then fields full of strawberries that were broken, full of bacteria that can no longer be eliminated after the harvest. all would arrive mouldy in the supermarket. Disposal rate more because of such factors than, for example, too long delivery routes. 99.999% of the harvested fruit will find its way into the trade. factors: optics play a major role. More difficult to sell a product with a shell defect than a product with a shell defect. If parasites and technology destroy the fruit inside and not visible from the outside (paprika pest not visible with scan or x-ray). Also with parasites human feeling, common sense is in demand. Know-how transfer. <p>Estimated price of technology: EUR 70,000</p>						

-	Fairtrade CH	-	23/04/19 WU	Phone	PMi, ST	GER
Contacts given: Westfalia, Georges Helfer, Giovanelli						

-	Lindt & Sprüngli	-	23/04/19 WU	Phone	PMi, ST	GER
Not interested in participating in the project.						

Gunar Nakladal	Frutura GmbH	Ripening manager	15/05/19 WU	Phone	BL, ST	GER
Fruits come unripe from overseas.						
Avocados: very hard and green, treated with moisture and heat, circulating air, should not dry out, at 18 degrees 2-4 days post-ripening.						
Mangos: do not change externally, 3-6 days post-ripening. Mangoes are relatively unripe harvested.						
Next step: sorting.						

Criteria: Weight, degree of maturity. Partner in the sorting process: Austrian company in southern Styria, optical measuring method, red green-blue camera and infrared.

Infrared can check 1-2mm deep, deeper is not possible, but would be desirable, compromise near infrared system can measure 1-2mm the most important parameter. The company would like to have it deeper, but the technology does not make this possible, because it comes from material testing where homogeneous materials are usually examined. However, they do not want to use X-rays, as this does not correspond to their values (nature). Infrared is therefore a compromise. Because they cannot see the inside of the fruit - no inner browning, rot, etc...

There is interest (because infrared does not get to the inner core of the fruit) for a technology that makes this possible - without using X-rays. That would be very forward-looking. Technology costs several million euros. This will be difficult to afford for fruit trading companies.

Research by the University of Laimburg in South Tyrol and the University of Davis in California in these fields.

Sergio Giovanelli	Giovanelli	Manager	16/05/19 WU	Phone	BL, ST	GER
<p>Many firms do research on this topic themselves; the apple industry might be the one which could be most interested in this topic and have many insights how far this technology has already been developed.</p> <p>Giovanelli is a company for stone fruit, berries, mushrooms and exotic fruits such as mangos, avocados and papayas. It sorts itself by hand, as there is no machine yet that can measure the inner values of the fruit correctly - so they sort by hand. "simple and simple He thinks that the water content will be too inaccurate for a concrete measurement.</p> <p>For mangos and avocados, we have been looking for a suitable technique for 10 years. Sorting systems like Aweta and Kopak can do everything the same or cannot do all the same. Machine with technology for the internal condition would be an extreme competitive advantage.</p> <p>Giovanelli is sorting itself stone-fruit - mushrooms and exotic mangos, avocados For mangos and avocado there is no sorting technology right now, so they have to sort by hand Aweta and Kopak are nameable sorting machine producers</p> <p>It is not possible to correctly test the intrinsic value of a fruit although the dry content measurement is a common method and easy and fast to determine</p> <p>Current technologies are just able to check the first 3-4 mm of the fruit and are not very precise. That is why most fruit are graded by measuring the consistence by hand-pressure.</p> <p>Another problem is the ripening during the transportation-process, which leads to short shelf lives of avocados, papayas and mangos. Parasites are not a big problem in these fruits or fruits in general.</p> <p>In Styria they are developing sorting machines, which approximately are about 250.000€. The price depends on how many products can be sorted. The industry would be willing to pay about EUR 250,000 for CERNs technology.</p>						

Lothar Wurm	HBLA Klosterneuburg Wein- und Obstbau	Director of orcharding	16/05/19 WU	Phone	BL, ST	GER
<p>There are two types of fruits: climacteric and non-climacteric fruits.</p> <p>Climacteric fruits: post ripening process for action, harvested unripe. The hormone ethylene increases towards ripeness, cellular respiration increases, water is respired, sugar transformed into CO₂. The rate can be measured with CO₂ content: if CO₂ amount is very high = respiration high → ripeness. Water content decreases within ripening process due to transpiration. Water release during storage leads to a quality a weight loss. The extent depends on humidity in the storage area. It is better if storage is damp and cold.</p> <p>During ripeness process: fruit flesh firmness decreases, through respiration organic substances decrease, sugar and organic acids, fats and heat is released, conversion of substances, starch is converted to sugar → thus the fruit tastes sweeter, aromas are built up. Ethylene plays an important role; it is driving the ripeness. It is possible to block ethylene.</p> <p>Non-climacteric fruits: to harvest in a ripe stadium Storage losses - parasitic storage diseases - physiological quality loss (biochemical process does not run optimally, bitter pit is the most important storage disease, induced by calcium deficiency)</p>						

-	Müller Transporte	-	10/05/19 WU	Phone	BL, ST	GER
No sorting, forwarding agency. Customers are for example San Lucar. Also import from the Netherlands.						

Petra Pettolaz, Barbara Galli, Frederic Verborg	Chiquita	Marketing, Head of Marketing R&D	23/05/19 WU	Video conference	BL, ST	EN
Chiquita does not use machines, harvest fruits based on visual criteria (colour indicates ripeness level); bananas are harvested when they are green (very important) and put into clusters; very important to stop the ripening process!; sometimes still ripen and boxes have to be thrown away (very low throwaway quota though); ripening by using ethylene; not a lot of parasites for bananas exist; bananas very low margin products so quantity is important! ; manpower for sorting important in order to create jobs; they do not really see a benefit in the technology since waste is already very, very low						

Theo Bekker	Westfalia	Operations Manager: Technological Services	23/05/19 WU	Phone	BL, ST	EN
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Westfalia mainly grows mangoes and avocados, sorting consists of different stages: video sorting in the field, afterwards fruits are delivered to a packing house; then go into a visual sorting system -> distribution to the local market or into the export market (but sorting process depends on the crop)
 Not a lot of waste involved since they produce juice, oil or even guacamole, waste under 10%
 Not a big fan of machines, since they take away work for the local communities (important due to social responsibility)
 Cannot estimate the value – no interest in the technology

Franz Kafka	METRO	Category Manager	23/05/19 WU	Phone	ST	EN
Provided further contacts: Bratzler, and Wegscheider (QM Metro)						

Dipl.-Ing. Eva Wegscheider	METRO	Head of QM	23/05/19 WU	Phone	BL, ST	EN
10% of fruits have to be checked before distribution to supermarkets; based on visual procedures, time is the key, human resources are cheaper, and it is more time efficient, supermarkets do not have the right capacities for sorting, every supplier has its own expertise						

Peter Heftberger	EFKO	Operations Manager	08/05/19 WU	Phone	PMi, ST	GER
Efko sorts some of the harvested fruit itself and has some of it sorted externally. The current sorting process uses cameras to detect the colour and shape of the fruit, which indicates its ripeness and weight. Other fruits such as potatoes are sorted manually. The biggest problem is the accuracy of sorting with cameras: if you set the camera even more precisely, the failure rate would in principle be exorbitantly high. Basically, there would be an interest in the CERN technology, there is too little space at the moment because such a sorting machine is very space consuming. The price of the machine is estimated at 0,5 million euros. Pickles are also sorted by the machine itself. New contact: Thomas Sachleitner.						

Valéry Courvoisier	Georges Helfer	Operating manager	22/05/19 WU	Phone	BL, ST	GER
Sort manually through vision grading, no capacities to acquire a machine, further contacts: Mehadrin, Hall's, Cool Control						

Dr. Martin Gössinger	HBLA Klosterneuburg Obst- und Weinbau	Principal of HBLA Klosterneuburg	16/05/19 WU	Phone	BL, ST	GER
Explained the ripening process of fruits again, NMR can detect parasites since worms increase the air content in the fruit due to its holes; different methods for sorting and grading: infrared, vision, X-ray...						

Jaap Kosse	University of Twente	Phd student	17/05/19 WU	Phone	PMi	EN
Mr. Kosse helped the New Business Development project from 2017 with their project with his expertise for NMR Spectroscopy. He explained how the water-content of a fruit or another test subject can be measured, by magnetizing it and checking the objects magnetic field afterwards with a coil. He thinks the technology could determine the inner characteristics of eggs too, but thinks the scanning process might take too long.						

Ronald Wagner	Wagnerguss GmbH	Director	21.05.2019 WU	Phone	MPe	GE
Mister Wagner gave quality insights on how the smelting and casting process works at the company. He also mentioned companies that produce furnaces which are regarded as industry standard and gave useful technical information about them.						

Walter Hafner	Eisenwerk Sulzau-Werfen R. & E. Weinberger AG	Engineer	21.05.2019 WU	Phone	MPe	GE
Mister Hafner explained why the furnace is not relevant for iron smelting and gave information about the furnaces the company currently is using and what capacity they have. He explained the process of how the procurement of new furnaces works. The company makes a yearly reserve for future purchases.						

Gabor Bardocz	Nemak Linz GmbH	Engineer	21.05.2019 WU	Phone	MPe	GE
Mister Bardocz explained the company's smelting and casting process. He also went into detail with how their furnaces work and that the main driver when buying new furnaces is purchasing costs and operating costs and that the features of the newly developed furnace are not as relevant when making buying decisions.						

Magnus Ek	Boliden	Furnace Specialist	23/05/19 WU	Phone	HS	EN
Talked about the significance of the special properties of the furnace. Furthermore, gave some key insights needed in industries apart from the aluminum industry and their current budget for furnace technologies. Referred to some major furnace manufacturers as well as to companies that could be of relevance. Gave some details about their process of minimizing oxidation.						

Monika Handblum	Boliden	Employee of R&D	23/05/19 WU	Phone	HS	EN
Assessed the attractiveness of the special properties of the furnace. Went into special depth about the temperature variations as well as the homogenous heating of the furnace. Referred to Magnus Ek for further assessment of the Furnace.						
Shailesh Chandrol	Outotec	Head of Market Area Sales, Metals, Energy and Water	23/05/19 WU	Phone	HS	EN
Provided very crucial information about the general strategy of furnace manufactures in Europe compared to manufactures in Asia. Went into detail on the general assessment of furnace technologies by scrap metal recycling companies and their openness to innovation. Clarified who needs to pay the penalty if the technology causes damages and that all companies have commercial contractual penalties. Furthermore, he explained that the industry is very conservative.						
Scheele Georg	Trimet	Head of Foundry	17/05/19 WU	Phone	HS	EN
Assessed the attractiveness of the special properties of the furnace in detail for his firm. Went into special detail about the future of eco-friendly electricity in combination with furnace technologies and tried to analyze the current downsides of electric furnaces. Furthermore, connected us to the R&D department for further information.						
Peter Robatscher	Versuchszentrum Laimburg	Researcher	11/0619 WU	Phone	BL, ST	GE
Mission to introduce NMR to the market -> great potential?: " I don't think it's possible. " apple then still needs to be cut – >not 100% non-invasive (aromas, vitamins, etc.. have to be determined through laboratory testing); first customers could be Fruit producers, cooperatives. For a Higher quality -> higher price; question arises what happens to the fruits that deviate from the premium standard; NMR has to be fast -> screening time has to be less than 1 min						
Richard Glössl	Kröpfel F. Obsthandels-gesmbh	Operating Manager	11/0619 WU	Phone	BL, ST	GE
Sorting is done via optical cameras (color). Apples are put into rotation, multiple pictures are taken. Afterwards their diameter, length and quality are measured. Infrared is also used (Apple in 64 slices "figuratively cut", then analyzed with infrared) 25 tons per hour are sorted: 8 apples per second, 8 lines -> 320,000 pieces per hour theoretically possible. What else should be measured?-> Sugar content correlation – but sometimes misleading. Need a technology that can measure 50 different quality parameters.						
Anonymous	Aludium	Manager	21/0619 WU	Phone	HS	GE
Discussed the use benefits of the furnace and assessed them according to their relevance for the aluminum industry. Furthermore, we talked especially about the size of their new furnace and their role in tackling sustainability in the industry as well as the relevance of argon as a protection against oxidation.						
Mario Löbbs	Aurubis	Head of R&D	21/0619 WU	Phone	HS	GE
Dr. Löbbs is the head of R&D at Aurubis and during the interview he elaborated on the relevance of the furnaces use benefits in their industries. Aurubis recycled precious metals and especially copper, nickel, platinum and Zink. Furthermore, he explained that compared to the Aluminum industry, oxidation is of much bigger concern since it implies the loss of valuable resources						
Lorenz Canaval	Montanwerke Brixlegg	Head of Quality Management	16/05/19 WU	Phone	HS	GE
In the interview we discussed the use benefits of the furnace technology and assessed their relevance within their industry.						
Helmut Andrekowitzsch	Montan Universität Leoben	University Professor	17/0519 WU	Phone	BL,HS	GE
Dr. Löbbs is the head of R&D at Aurubis and during the interview he elaborated on the relevance of the furnaces use benefits in their industries. Aurubis recycled precious metals and especially copper, nickel, platinum and Zink. Furthermore, he explained that compared to the Aluminum industry, oxidation is of much bigger concern since it implies the loss of valuable resources						
Oleg Hoffmann	BAGR Berlin Aluminiumwerk GmbH	Head of Smelting Operations	21/06/19 WU	Phone	HS	GE
Oleg Hoffmann acts as the head of smelting operations at BAGR Berlin Aluminiumwerk GmbH. He helped to assess the use benefits of the furnace technology. Generally, he said that heat homogeneity is not relevant since the needed level is already reached. Furthermore, he added that for aluminum recycling the temperature preciseness is only of marginal relevance in contrast to heat -treatment. He then added that Argon is to expensive to use as a protection from oxidation.						